

Scientific Article: German-Uzbek Legal Press Language

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Abstract: This article examines the legal press language in the German and Uzbek legal systems and analyzes the key differences and similarities between the two languages. The focus is on the use of legal terminology, communication clarity, and the grammatical and stylistic aspects in both systems. The article explores the challenges and opportunities of legal press language in both countries and discusses the importance of clear and precise language to effectively communicate legal topics to the public. The analysis includes various legal text types, including legislative texts, court rulings, and legal reporting in the media.

Keywords: Legal Press Language, German-Uzbek Legal Comparison, Legal Terminology, Legal Communication, Legal Reporting, Linguistic Clarity, Grammar and Style, Translation of Legal Documents.

Introduction:

The legal press language plays a crucial role in the communication of legal information within society. In Germany and Uzbekistan, two countries with different legal traditions and language systems, there are significant differences in how legal information is presented in the media. These differences are influenced not only by language but also by cultural and institutional factors. Therefore, the study of legal press language in both countries is essential for developing a better understanding of legal communication and its impact on the public.

Main Section:

In the German legal system, legal terms are clearly defined and standardized. The use of technical terms and adherence to grammatical norms are essential for precise and clear communication. In Uzbekistan, however, legal press language is often characterized by a certain level of complexity, and legal terminology is sometimes used in a broader context. Another feature of Uzbek legal press language is the influence of the Russian language, which can lead to ambiguities and misunderstandings.

Legal Terminology and Clarity of Communication:

In both countries, the precise use of legal terminology is of paramount importance. While in Germany, legal terminology is highly regulated, there is still room for further development and standardization of technical terms in Uzbekistan. Especially in the translation of legal documents between German and Uzbek, challenges arise because the two languages have different legal concepts and expressions.

Grammatical and Stylistic Aspects:

Another aspect of legal press language is the grammatical and stylistic structuring of texts. In

Germany, legal texts are usually formal, precise, and structured. In Uzbekistan, there is greater flexibility in expression, which can sometimes compromise clarity and comprehensibility. In both countries, it is crucial that legal texts are accessible to the general public without compromising legal accuracy.

Conclusion:

The German-Uzbek legal press language shares both similarities and differences. Both legal systems strive for clarity and precision in communication, although various linguistic and cultural challenges exist. The further development of a standardized legal terminology in Uzbekistan and the promotion of clear, understandable language are crucial for enhancing the effectiveness of legal press language. Close cooperation and exchange between the two countries in the field of legal communication could lead to better comprehensibility and transparency in legal reporting.

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